

EVALUATION OF THE ARTISTIC GYMNASTICS DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

ОЦІНКА ПРОГРАМИ РОЗВИТКУ ХУДОЖНЬОЇ ГІМНАСТИКИ

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Abstract

This study aims to: 1) Know how the role of the trainer in coaching and developing the artistic gymnastics of Cilacap Regency. 2) Knowing how the training program for coaching and developing achievements in artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency. 3) Knowing how to manage management and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency. 4) Knowing how to evaluate the implementation of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency. 5) Knowing how the facilities and infrastructure for the development and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency. 6) Knowing what obstacles are in the achievement of artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency.

This research is an evaluative study with a context, input, process, product (CIPP) model. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling technique. The data collection techniques in this evaluative research are observation and questionnaires (questionnaires). The method used in this research is a questionnaire method using a Likert scale. The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive analysis, namely by describing and interpreting the data from each of the components being evaluated.

The results showed that the coach was able to carry out coaching well, he was able to discipline athletes, and the administrators were also able to make good management in the organization. There needs to be regeneration of athletes and understanding of sports actors in producing potential athletes. Sports coaching is organized in a planned, integrated and sustainable manner. Quality and quantity infrastructure and facilities support. The obstacles identified were athlete factors, coach factors, equipment and facilities factors, quality factors and competition quantity factors. Organizational factors, namely funding, organizational management, and coordination. The conclusion obtained from this research is that the program of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in the Cilacap regency gymnastics club is well organized.

Key words: Evaluation, Coaching, Sports, Artistic Gymnastics.

Це дослідження має на меті: 1) Знати яка роль тренера у навчанні та розвитку художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство. 2) Знати роль програми тренувань та розвитку досягнень у художній гімнастиці в Чилакап Регентство. 3) Знати, як керувати управлінням та розвитком досягнень художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство. 4) Знати, як оцінити впровадження коучингу та розвитку досягнень художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство. 5) Знання зручностей та інфраструктури для розвитку та досягнень художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство. 6) Знання того, що перешкоджає досягненням художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство.

Це дослідження є оціночним вивченням з контекстом, вхідними даними, процесом, продуктом (КВПП) моделі. Методика вибірки, використана у цьому дослідженні, була цільовою технікою вибірки. Методами збору даних у цьому оціночному дослідженні є спостереження та опитування (анкети). Метод, використаний у цьому дослідженні, – це опитувальний метод за шкалою Лікерта. Метод аналізу даних, використаний у цьому дослідженні, – це описовий аналіз, а саме шляхом опису та інтерпретації даних кожного з компонентів, що оцінюються.

Результати показали, що тренер зміг добре виконувати тренерську роботу, він зміг дисциплінувати спортсменів, а адміністратори також змогли добре керувати організацією. Потрібна регенерація спортсменів та розуміння спортивних функціонерів для розвитку потенційних спортсменів. Спортивне тренування організується планово, комплексно та стійко. Підтримка інфраструктури та об'єктів якості та кількості. Визначеними перешкодами були фактори спортсмена, фактори тренера, фактори оснащення та обладнання, фактори якості та фактори конкуренції. Організаційні фактори, а саме фінансування, організаційне управління та координація. Висновок, отриманий з цього дослідження, полягає в тому, що програма тренування та розвитку досягнень художньої гімнастики в Чилакап Регентство гімнастичному клубі є добре організованою.

Ключові слова: оцінювання, коучинг, спорт, художня гімнастика.

Introduction. Advances in science and technology clearly have a broad impact on the development of training theory and methodology (Eubank et al., 2017). Careful preparation and a systematically arranged training program are absolutely necessary (Marcora & Sarkar, 2018).

There are many obstacles that have often been faced, some of which are short training sessions, only a few months (Avdeeva & Tulyakova, 2018). The short duration of training will clearly have an impact on the less than optimal achievement of peak performance, resulting in not optimal results

(Sealey & Tope, 2011). Even though the main goal of practicing players is to achieve peak performance in the main competition when a competition is held (Richardson et al., 2020). For this reason, athlete development must be planned properly and correctly and be based on the concept of periodization and the principles of training as well as the methodology for its application in the field (Aprilia et al., 2018).

The most complex and challenging problem in training methodology is how to achieve peak performance at a planned date and time (Pasichnyk et al., 2021). Peak performance is not achieved by accident (Marrier et al., 2017). The creation of peak performance is the result of careful preparation of athletes, based on a detailed organized training program, planned in stages, objectively and continuously (Hollings et al., 2014). Peak performance is a direct result of the athlete's adaptation to various systems, methods and forms of training (Jackson & Roberts, 2016). In an effort to formulate an exercise program to improve achievement, four aspects must be considered, namely (1) physical aspects, (2) techniques, (3) tactics and (4) mental aspects. These four aspects must be trained in the right way and method so that each aspect can develop optimally (Aubry et al., 2014).

Sports coaching for the achievement of Floor Gymnastics cannot be done in an instant way (Root et al., 2019). Especially when there is no management from the road, but it requires totality and commitment to fostering sports in a systemic and supportive manner (Norouzi et al., 2020). Sports achievement is something that is both observable and measurable (Thomas & Thomas, 2019). Meaning that sports coaching is carried out

with a scientific approach ranging from talent scouting to the coaching process (Moeskops et al., 2019). A systemic point of view that the quality of the results (output) is determined by input and the quality of the coaching process that occurs (Longo et al., 2016). The achievements that have been obtained so far are a real consequence of the sub-system that is less than optimal, namely input and process (Mkaouer et al., 2018).

The approach used in this program evaluation research is the CIPP Model (Daniel Stufflebeam's) in terms of the context, input, process and product stages (Stufflebeam & Coryn, 2014). The point is to obtain accurate and objective information and compare what has been achieved from the Floor Gymnastics Development program in Cilacap Regency. With what should be achieved based on established standards.

Methods. This research is an evaluative study with a context, input, process, product (CIPP) model. The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling technique. Data collection techniques in this evaluative research are observation and questionnaires (questionnaires). The method used in this research is a questionnaire method using a Likert scale. The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive analysis by describing and interpreting the data from each component being evaluated.

Results and Discussion. The results of the research on the evaluation of the artistic gymnastics performance development program in the Cilacap regency gymnastics club will be described in detail the results of the research that have been carried out by the researcher as follows:

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of the evaluation of the achievement coaching program artistic gymnastics at the Cilacap regency gymnastics club

		The role of coach	Exercise program	Coaching management	Implementation evaluation	Facilities and infrastructure
N	Valid	36	36	36	36	36
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.450	3,5278	3.4500	3,4306	3.4124
Std. Deviation		.62405	.55888	.53532	.62218	.48307
Variance		.389	.312	.287	.387	.233
Minimum		1.92	2.00	2.20	1.83	2.15
Maximum		4.00	4.00	4.00	3.92	3.85

From the table above it can be explained that all aspects such as the role of the trainer, training programs, coaching management, implementation evaluation, facilities and infrastructure are in good category. Because after processing the data using the SPSS software, it shows the mean range from 3.26 to 4.00 as in the evaluation criteria table and the meaning of the evaluation. The percentage details are as follows:

1. The role of a coach in the coaching and development of artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency

The achievement of targets cannot be separated from the ability of a coach to shape his athletes from ordinary to extraordinary athletes. Thus, if the organizers of performance coaching want high achievement targets, they must look for a coach who has the appropriate qualifications for their sport and has experience in training athletes to excel. Below are the results of a questionnaire to describe the role of the coach in fostering artistic gymnastics achievements in the Cilacap regency gymnastics club as follows:

Table 2

The role of coach in the artistic gymnastics sports achievement development program in the Cilacap regency gymnastics club

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not good	6	16.7	16.7	16.7
	Good	30	83.3	83.3	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

From the data table above, it can be described that the role of the coach in the coaching program of artistic gymnastics achievement in the Cilacap regency

gymnastics club, the results were 83.3% in the good category and 16.7% in the poor category. The percentage acquisition chart can be seen below:

Graph 1. The role of the trainer

2. Training program for coaching and developing achievements in artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency

Performance development will run well if it is organized and disciplined by all parties

concerned. Below is a discussion about the implementation of the training program as follows:

Table 3

Training program for coaching and developing achievements in artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not good	4	11.1	11.1	11.1
	Pretty good	2	5.6	5.6	16.7
	Good	30	83.3	83.3	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

From the data table above, it can be described that the training program for coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievement in Cilacap Regency is 83.3% in the

good category, 11.1% in the poor category, and 5.6% in the good enough category. The percentage acquisition chart can be seen below:

Graph 2. Exercise Program

3. Management of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency

To run programs owned by an organization, it is necessary to have good management in accordance with its fields. Below is a discussion of coaching management as follows:

Table 4

Management of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not good	4	11.1	11.1	11.1
	Pretty good	3	8.3	8.3	19.4
	Good	29	80.6	80.6	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

From the data table above, it can be described that the management of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency is 80.6% in

the good category, 11.1% in the poor category, and 8.3% in the good enough category. The percentage acquisition chart can be seen below:

Graph 3. Exercise Management

4. Evaluation of the implementation of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics sports achievements in Cilacap Regency

Evaluation of the implementation of the program, to obtain information about the

effectiveness of implementation and the achievement of the results, then the information obtained can be used to make further decisions regarding the program being implemented. Below is a discussion of the evaluation of the implementation of coaching as follows:

Table 5

Evaluation of the implementation of coaching and performance development of artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not good	6	16.7	16.7	16.7
	Pretty good	2	5.6	5.6	22.2
	Good	28	77.8	77.8	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

From the data table above, it can be described that the evaluation of the implementation of coaching and development of artistic gymnastics achievement in Cilacap

Regency is 77.8% in the good category, 16.7% in the poor category, and 5.6% in the good enough category. The percentage acquisition chart can be seen below:

Graph 4. Implementation Evaluation

5. Facilities and infrastructure for fostering and developing achievements in artistic gymnastics in Cilacap Regency

Sports infrastructure and facilities are very important to support the coaching and development of sports, especially sports

achievements. The sports infrastructure and facilities needed for sports coaching and development should meet national or even international standards. Below is a discussion of the following development facilities and infrastructure:

Table 6

Facilities and infrastructure for guidance and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not good	4	11.1	11.1	11.1
	Pretty good	3	8.3	8.3	19.4
	Good	29	80.6	80.6	100.0
	Total	36	100.0	100.0	

From the data table above, it can be described that the facilities and infrastructure for the development and development of artistic gymnastics achievements in Cilacap Regency

are 80.6% in good category, 11.1% in poor category, and 8.3% in good enough category. The percentage acquisition chart can be seen below:

Graph 6. facilities and infrastructure

Conclusion. The results showed that the coach was able to carry out coaching well, he was able to discipline athletes, and the administrators were also able to make good management in the organization. There needs to be regeneration of athletes and understanding of sports actors in producing potential athletes. Sports coaching is organized in a planned, integrated and sustainable manner. Quality and quantity infrastructure and facilities support.

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